

Paper 1

SOCIAL SKILLS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN RELATION TO GENDER AND LOCALITY

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ABSTRACT

In this study, concerted effort was made to study the Social Skills among Secondary School Students in terms of Gender and Locality. Social Skills are observable behaviors that individuals exhibit to perform competently on a social task like active listening, interpersonal relationships, the understanding of others feeling, etc. The present study was descriptive in nature. A survey has been undertaken to study the Social Skills among Secondary School Students with respect to gender, and locality, by administering a 'Rating Scale on Social Skills'. The three dimensions of Social Skills such as "Interpersonal, Communication and Concern for others" were measured through a five point scale having twenty two statements. The sample of the study involved 462 Secondary School students pursuing the state syllabus in different schools of Mangalore Taluk situated in Urban and Rural areas selected through simple Random sampling technique. The findings revealed that social Skills of Urban Secondary School students are significantly higher than that of Rural School students. It also revealed that Social skills among secondary school students do not differ in terms of gender.

Key words: Social Skill, Interpersonal skill, Communication Skill Concern for others and Secondary School Students.

Introduction:

The progress of society depends upon the nature of education. Education is the fundamental right of everyone and capable of bringing any desired change and up lift ment in the human mind and society. One of the most significant aims of education is the harmonious development of the individual. Social skill is any competence facilitating interaction and communication with others where social rules and relations are created, communicated and changed in verbal and non-verbal ways. The process of learning these skills is called socialization.

Social skills are skills we need to interact and adapt in our cultural environment. Social skills play a very important role in a child's emotional health and well-being. The present education is concerned only with the academic achievement of the students and hence it emphasizes on the development of cognitive skills. Learning is essential for students to master skills but if the affective domain is

ignored, the cognitive areas are greatly affected. It is difficult to achieve even the highest levels in the cognitive domain, if the complementary skills in the affective domain are not developed.

Social skills are the tools that enable people to communicate, learn, ask for help, get needs met in appropriate ways, get along with others, make friends, develop healthy relationships, protect themselves, and in general, be able to interact with the society harmoniously. Social Skills build essential character traits like trustworthiness, respectfulness, responsibility, fairness, caring, and citizenship. These traits help build an internal moral compass, allowing individuals to make good choices in thinking and behaviour, resulting in social competence.

Social skills imply goal directed and well organized behaviors like Communication skills, Interpersonal Skills and Concern for others. Communication is conveying information thoughts and feeling to others meaningfully. It involves empathy and sensitivity towards others. Interpersonal skills come hand in hand with communication as students will learn how to relate well to other people if they learn both skills. It able to make and keep friendly relationships, which can be of great importance to their mental and social wellbeing.

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Rationale for the study

Adolescence is a developmental stage in which significant changes happen in all aspects of physical, cognitive, emotional and social. These changes create a new feeling of identity in adolescents and lead them toward socialization with its entire emergence of developing a distinct identity. These features, along with a sense of attachment to the peer group, their vulnerability has been higher than other groups.

The study conducted by Rajesh and Chandrasekaran (2013) on Interpersonal Skill of college student's revealed significant difference in students Interpersonal Skills with respect to their Gender, Degree Studying, Medium of Instruction, Residential Locality and Type of Family. The study also revealed that no significant difference in students Interpersonal Skills with respect to their Stream of the Study, Type of College Management and Number of Siblings.

Shimsiya and Sincy Issac (2016) conducted a study on Social Skills among Secondary School Student's in Relation to Gender and Locale. Results reveal that there exists a significant difference in

the mean scores of social skills among secondary school students in relation to gender and locale of the school.

Daraee Minoos & Maryam Fakhr (2016) conducted a study on comparison of the social skills of students in ordinary schools and talented schools. The results revealed that the students of talented schools are significantly higher in appropriate social skills and are overconfident, but no significant difference was observed in other components.

Eshrat Zamani (2010) conducted a study on social skills of students addicted to computer games with normal students. The results of the study revealed that normal students had a higher level of social skills in comparison with students addicted to computer games.

The study conducted by Devi, Mukesh and Chahar (2015) revealed that academic achievement has significant dependence on social skills of school students.

Objectives of the study

- To study the Social Skills among the Secondary School Students in terms of gender
- To study the Social Skills among the Secondary School Students in terms of locality of schools.

Hypotheses of the study

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the Social Skills of Boys and Girls of Secondary School.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the Social Skills of Rural and Urban Students of Secondary School.

Methodology

The present study was descriptive in nature. A survey has been conducted to study the Social Skills among Secondary School Students with respect to gender and Locality by administering a 'Rating Scale on Social Skills'. The three dimensions of Social Skills such as Interpersonal Skills, Communication Skills and Concern for others were measured through a five point scale having twenty two statements. The sample of the study involved 462 Secondary School students with 168 boys and 294 girls pursuing state syllabus in different schools of Mangalore Taluk situated in Urban and Rural areas selected through simple Random sampling technique. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. Inferential statistic 't' test was used to test the significance of the

difference in Social Skills with respect to gender, and locality. Hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

Objective One: To study the Social Skills among the Secondary School Students in terms of gender

Table 1: 't' test Details of the Social Skills among Secondary school Boys and Girls

Gender	N	M	SD	't' Value	Result
Girls	294	85.16	12.53	1.91	Not Significant
Boys	168	82.67	13.91		

From the Table 1, it is observed that the obtained 't' value 1.91 is lesser than the table value 1.97 at 0.05 level of significance with of 460. Hence the null hypothesis "There is no significant difference in the Social Skills of Boys and Girls of Secondary School" is accepted and it is concluded that boys and girls of secondary school students do not differ in their Social Skills.

Objective Two: To study the Social Skills among the Secondary School Students in terms of locality of schools.

Table 2: 't' test Details of the Social Skills of Rural and Urban students

Locality	N	M	SD	't' Value	Result
Rural	105	89.12	10.50	5.07	Significant
Urban	357	82.83	13.45		

From the Table 2, it is observed that the obtained 't' value 5.07 is higher than the table value 1.97 at 0.05 level of significance with of 460. Hence the null hypothesis "There is no significant difference in the Social Skills of Rural and Urban Students of Secondary School" is rejected and it is concluded that Secondary School students of Rural and Urban schools differ in their Social Skills. Social Skills of Urban secondary schools' students are significantly higher than the Rural Secondary school students since the mean score of urban school student is higher than the Rural.

Findings of the study:

- There is no significant difference in the Social Skills of Boys and Girls of Secondary school Students

- There is significant difference in the Social skills of Rural and Urban Students of Secondary School

Conclusion:

The study revealed that Social Skills of Urban Secondary School Students is significantly higher than that of Rural School Students. It implies that schools should provide appropriate curricular and co-curricular activities to enhance their interpersonal skills, Communication skills and Concern for others. So that their Social Skills in general will enhance. The study also revealed that Social Skills among the Secondary school Students do not differ in terms of gender. It indicates that Social Skills are concerned; Secondary school Students of Mangaluru Taluk are equal irrespective of their gender.

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